

Agents for Change Agentes para a mudança

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Abstract

Agents for Change/Facing the Anthropocene presented artworks in 2020 at THE MUSEUM Kitchener, Canada by women media artists working at the intersection of science, technology and art, with a focus on nature and ecological change – the greatest danger of our time. Responding to the global recognition of the importance of the creative voices and activism of women artists, this unique exhibition demonstrates progress towards improving gender representation in the media arts.

Keywords: Interdisciplinary art, women artists, ecological change

Resumo

Agentes para a Mudança / Enfrentando o Antropoceno apresentaram obras de arte em 2020 em O MUSEU Kitchener, Canadá, por mulheres artistas de mídia que trabalham na interseção de ciência, tecnologia e arte, com foco na natureza e na mudança ecológica - o maior perigo de nosso tempo. Em resposta ao reconhecimento global da importância das vozes criativas e do ativismo de mulheres artistas, esta exposição única demonstra o progresso no sentido de melhorar a representação de gênero nas artes da mídia.

Palavras-chave: arte interdisciplinar, mulheres artistas, mudança ecológica

The impact of environmental change has begun to affect everyone –from rising sea levels to intense heat waves, to the mass extinction of the earth’s flora and fauna. Change is inevitable, but only by facing the future and understanding the challenges can we begin to become *Agents for Change*. *The Shore Line* by Elizabeth (Liz) Miller described as “ a storybook for the future, a collaborative, interactive documentary project with soundscapes visualization dynamic maps, educational resources and over forty videos illustrates the effects of the rising seas. Director Liz Miller features individuals who are confronting the threats of unsustainable development and extreme weather with persistence and ingenuity (Figure 1)

Environmental art and eco art activism is already manifested in the positive public reception of international exhibitions, conferences, films, literature and performances. There is a growing interest in the work of women artists. The projected audience and participatory impact of the *Agents for Change/Facing the Anthropocene* exhibition and

thematically linked discussions, lectures, workshops and performances are highly consequential. Diane Landry a participating artist from the Province of Quebec tells us: “My artistic practice through the use of re-contextualizing semi-ready made(s), asks the viewer to look twice and to see the world differently. The artwork juxtaposes the proposition of the perpetual Motion Machine, with sand and plastic bottles, to suggest an infinite and self-perpetuating problem linked to energy, water resources and lack of recycling” (Figure 2).

The goal of my own thematic curatorial practice is focused on creating broader public/audience awareness for specific topical issues including environmental change. *Behold the Tilapia* by Kristine Diekman considers the history, mythology and the current decline of Tilapia in California’s Salton Sea, a man-made sea that is quickly evaporating due to climate change and depleted waterways. *Behold the Tilapia* is an attempt to resurrect the importance of the fish while acknowledging the forces that contribute to the decline (Figure 3). *Spirits of Wasteland* by Maayke Schurer continues a process of re-creating scenarios that consider human activity in the natural environment. Miniaturized scenes are filmed real-time without effects to provide opportunity for reflection on our place within nature. The scenes are prompted by such questions as “What does light look like shining through islands of ocean plastic...” (Figure 4)

Nature may be considered as the world of living organism and their environment; in a larger sense the shape of Nature can also be understood to include particular extents of space and time. *Drone* by Donna Legault is an immersive installation where the light from multiple video projections modulate audio signals in real-time. When participants enter the array of speakers they are surrounded by sounds that affect the experience of being within a beehive. The work exposes research in the US and Japan that is aimed at replacing the dwindling bee population with micro-robotic counterparts (Figure 5). *Sounding: Sounding Walks and Sounding CA* by Caroline McCaw and Vicki Smith from New Zealand considers the effects of pollution on marine mammals. Whales and dolphins use echolocation – reflected sound- to navigate, communicate and hunt.

Sounding uses umbrellas to create both static and ambulatory experiences for audiences to immerse in the sound of our seas and mammals communication, via invisible digital oceans (Figure 6).

The visual perspectives of Nature form a particular course that begins with the earliest historical depictions and might be currently expressed by a variety of' cross-disciplinary contributions. The diverse perspectives form eclectic threads that today are frequently manifested within the Eco-activist movement. *Spontaneous Generation* by Elaine Whittaker claims that the notion that vermin spring fully formed from rubbish and decay seems ludicrous today. Climate change feeds another kind of alarm – a warmer planet generating a profound increase in hosts and vectors of pathogenic microbes. Are we ready for a post-glacial planet where temperatures rise mosquitoes reign, and microbes fester? (Figure 7)

An Ecosystem of Excess by Pinar Yoldas starts in the Great Pacific Garbage Patch. Covering 1.5 million square kilometers, the site is a monument to plastic waste on a global scale. *An Ecosystem of Excess* asks a simple question. “If life started today in our plastic debris filled oceans, what kinds of life forms would emerge out of this contemporary primordial ooze? (Figure 8) *Swamp Radio. Fluctuations of Microworlds* created by Rasa Smite and Raitis Smits consists of six “bacteria battery” cells, built by using Microbial Fuel Cell technology, which generates electrical energy from microorganisms – bacteria found in the soil, sediments of the pond or sewage. Electrical impulses and fluctuations of “bacteria electricity” make audible and visible the embedded activity found in nature, thus creating the poetics of green energy (Figure 9).

Anthrop Ocean by Olga Kisseleva is an interactive web-based project that asks the audience to question one’s own impact on the environment, which we continuously adjust to fall in-line with our own aspirations. The project provides access to a database devoted to issues relating to climate change, as well as the broader ties between, ocean, climate and society (Figure 10).

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Several of the contemporary ecological art works are grounded in explicit personal experiences and connections to specific places relevant to the sources where these were created – they form new models contributing to a speculative future culture

Fig1 *The Shore Line*, Elizabeth (Liz) Miller

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Fig2 *Knight of Infinite Resignation*, Diane Landry

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Fig3 *Behold the Tilapia*, Kristine Diekman

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Fig4 *Spirits of Wasteland*, Maayke Schurer

Fig5 *Drone*. Donna Legault

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Fig6 *Sounding: Sounding Walks and Sounding CA*_by Caroline McCaw and Vicki Smith

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Fig7 *Spontaneous Generation*, Elaine Whittaker

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Fig8 *An Ecosystem of Excess*, Pinar Yoldas

Fig9 *Swamp Radio Fluctuations of Microworlds* created by Rasa Smite and Raitis Smits

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Fig10 *Anthrop Ocean* by Olga Kisseleva